

Report on services in portability and refactoring Deliverable D3.2

About this document:

Work package in charge: WP3 HPC services to prepare the weather and climate community for the pre-exascale

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: 31st October 2022

Dissemination level: PU (for public use)

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1 Abstract

Weather and climate models are large and complex applications that experience a tension field between investments to enhance the numerical representation of the underlying physics, or to adapt the software to the latest hardware architectures (Lawrence et al., 2018). However, after a long period of relative stability, the computing infrastructure is rapidly evolving and diversifying, with more change on the horizon (Heldens et al., 2020). Adapting existing software to the latest computing platforms and exploiting the full capability of the architecture therefore requires specific expertise and extensive changes at the source code level (van Werkhoven et al., 2020). As such, continued development of weather and climate models requires new collaborations between experts from different fields (Müller et al., 2019).

ESiWACE2 supports the exascale preparations for the weather and climate modelling community in Europe through the creation of services. These services target the community at large, including both weather and climate modelling groups. The services establish short collaborative projects between Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and model development groups, providing guidance, engineering, and advice to improve model efficiency and port models to existing and upcoming computing infrastructures. This deliverable summarises the results from the service projects in portability and refactoring (Service 1) within the ESiWACE2 Services (Work Package 3) at the end of the project. It also discusses how to move forward and advance the codes towards exascale.

2 Conclusion & Results

The work presented in this deliverable is the result of collaborations between Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and model development groups created in the framework of ESiWACE2 services. These collaborations allowed a better understanding of the model performance behaviour and pave the way to a better use of the current and future HPC systems. A total of 10 applications have been studied, profiled, ported and optimised. The code is publicly available and results have been published and presented in conferences, journals and HPC events.

ESiWACE2 Service 1 reached its objective to bring together experts from different fields to create real impact in Earth system models performance and prepare them for the next generation of supercomputers towards exascale.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	✓
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	✓

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	✓
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	✗
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	✓
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	✗
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	✓
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	✓

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

ESiWACE2 aims to support the exascale preparations for the weather and climate modelling community in Europe through the creation of services. These services target the community at large, not just the ESiWACE2 partners, and include both weather and climate modelling groups. The services establish short collaborative projects between Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and model development groups, with the goal of providing guidance, engineering, and advice to improve model efficiency and port models to existing and upcoming computing infrastructures. Among the three proposed services, Service 1, named "portability and refactoring", targets weather and climate model developing groups by improving portability and performance. Service 1 uses open calls for proposals in order to select proposals that are technically feasible and have the highest priority for the weather and climate research communities.

This section presents a summary of the open calls process that we have established and a summary of work performed in each of the Service 1 projects.

4.1 Open calls for project service in portability and refactoring

From 2020 to 2022, ESiWACE2 has released each year an open call through which principal investigators (PIs) were able to apply for a service project to improve weather and climate model efficiency and scalability on existing and near-future High Performance Computing (HPC) systems. The idea of each project was to foster collaborations that provide consultancy and engineering efforts (6 person-months during one year) to support the exascale preparation of the weather and climate HPC community by enabling simulation experiments at unprecedented grid resolutions or ensemble sizes, or include computationally expensive physical processes that were previously unfeasible.

Particular attention has been paid to project proposals aiming at having a long-lasting impact on the source code of established models. In addition, we encouraged projects targeting accelerator hardware such as GPUs because these represent the most important source of computing power of current peta- and exa-scale HPC systems.

4.1.1 Service projects assessment procedure

The assessment of Service 1 proposals happened in two stages. First there was a technical review of the proposals by the RSEs at NLeSC and Atos. This review was not to assess the scientific impact, but rather focussed on the technical feasibility of the project: is the targeted performance improvement realistic, is the code practically portable to a new architecture within the timeline of the project, and can the underlying

numerical algorithm be accelerated? The outcome of the technical review was binding, only a selection of applications passed to the second round for scientific review. The final decision on the grant was made in the second stage by the scientific review committee of four scientists in the fields of weather and climate, with affinity for HPC, two of which were from within the ESiWACE2 project, and two were external reviewers.

4.2 Summary of the service project results

4.2.1 FESOM2

FESOM2 is a finite volume ocean circulation and sea ice model (Danilov et al., 2017; Koldunov et al., 2019). It solves the primitive equations using the hydrostatic and Boussinesq approximations on an unstructured grid, allowing seamless mesh resolution increase towards eddy-resolving scales in regions of high variability or along coast lines. FESOM2 is a highly optimised MPI-parallel Fortran code that displays excellent scaling to tens of thousands of cores. In the context of ESiWACE2 services, we have explored the benefits of GPU acceleration of FESOM2. We have determined the flux-corrected tracer transport, and in particular the advection of temperature and salinity, to be a dominant factor in the application profile, and we have ported this routine to GPUs using both CUDA-C¹ and OpenACC². The latter method has been preferred and extended as it offers a competitive performance with less development and maintenance effort. Profiling, loop nest extraction, characterisation and optimisation for both CPU and GPU have been performed on several representative test cases. However, re-integration of OpenACC directives and GPU-specific optimisation into the official code raised maintainability questions. A proposal has been implemented using a pre-processing tool³ to manage both CPU and GPU loop variants in the model. This work opens the doors for efficient deployment of FESOM2 on an exascale CPU- and GPU-based HPC system.

In this project, which lasted two years, the tracer transport module of FESOM2 has been ported using OpenACC, benchmarked and optimised. To define the best optimisation strategy using those OpenACC directives, kernels (the main time-consuming nested loops) have been extracted⁴. The kernels have been modified to get further performance gain on GPU (nearly 15-20 speed-up compared to the first OpenACC porting). Additionally, the project addressed CPU optimisations of the kernels that resulted in performance gains of 15 to 30%.

Final performance results are presented in detail in Table 1 on up to 12 compute nodes (i.e. 576 cores). Naïve openacc gives 2x speedup of tracer part for low core counts but speedup decreases at high multiplicity. Indeed, FESOM2 is a balanced code with many loops and thus partial port has limited effect.

Figure 1 presents the strong scalability at higher scale. About the scalability on GPUs, this is a known issue of GPUs since they need large domains to operate efficiently.

The advanced porting with loops collapsing also shows that beside the directives, the loops need to be modified. The code needs now two versions of the loops, one optimised for CPU, one optimised for GPU with the OpenACC directives. To ease the maintainability of the code, we propose to implement the characteristic loops of the code using FYPP macros.

The loops rewritten with FYPP have been reintegrated in the original code. It obviously shows the same speedup but it paves the way to now easily write an OpenMP port of FESOM2.

This work has been presented at the European Geosciences Union (EGU) (van den Oord et al., 2021).

¹<https://github.com/ESiWACE-S1/fesom2-accelerate>

²<https://github.com/ESiWACE-S1/fesom2>

³FYPP: <https://fypp.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html>

⁴<https://github.com/ESiWACE-S1/fesom2-kernels>

MPI tasks (nb compute nodes)	Mesh nodes per process	Tracer time (s)	Full time (s)	tracer speedup	full speedup
144 (3), cpu	38727	390	1061		
144 (3), acc	38727	178	863	2.19	1.22
144 (3), acc collapse	38727	167	859	2.33	1.23
288 (6), cpu	19363	195	511		
288 (6), acc	19363	92	415	2.11	1.23
288 (6), acc collapse	19363	86	415	2.26	1.23
576 (12), cpu	9682	97	260		
576 (12), acc	9682	48	210	2.02	1.23
576 (12), acc collapse	9682	45	209	2.15	1.24

Table 1: Detailed time and speedup observed after optimisations for the STORM benchmark case with different numbers of MPI tasks and compute nodes on the JUWELS-Booster supercomputer (2x CPU AMD EPYC ROME 24 cores and 4x GPU NVIDIA A100.)

Figure 1: Scaling of FESOM2 on CPU and GPU for the STORM benchmark on the JUWELS-Booster supercomputer (48 CPU cores per node and 4 GPUs per node).

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale To move forward, more parts of the code should be ported to GPU, such as dynamics, sea ice and SSH solver. Other interesting efforts should focus on Kernel optimisation to leverage $\text{acc collapse}(2)$ by replacing z-bounds with conditionals or pre-computed masks and on the support of CUDA-aware MPI to speed up halo exchanges in accelerated routines. Finally, it is also a good solution to merge OpenACC directives/optimisations with ongoing OpenMP parallelisation efforts.

4.2.2 DALES

The Dutch Atmospheric Large Eddy Simulation (DALES) (Heus et al., 2010) is a high-resolution three-dimensional solver focused on atmospheric boundary layer turbulence and cloud physics. It uses a rectangular grid of finite extent and periodic boundary conditions in the horizontal. DALES allows many choices in physical processes to be enabled (radiation, chemistry, etc) and numerical schemes (advection, microphysics); for the profiling and optimisation we have focused upon two use cases: (i) The simple and fast RICO benchmark case, which quickly becomes MPI-bound and useful for the parallel scaling optimisation, and (ii) the Ruisdael benchmark, which has radiation and atmospheric chemistry enabled and is therefore useful to assess the serial performance in real-world scenarios. The parallel scaling has been improved by incorporating a new iterative multi-grid solver for the pressure equation using the HYPRE library (<https://github.com/hypre-space/>

hypre). Although the old solver, based on the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), performs well in configurations with $\lesssim 5000$ MPI tasks, beyond this multiplicity the collective communications of the Fourier transform become a bottleneck. Beyond this problem size, the iterative solver surpasses the FFT-based approach (see Figure 2).

The new solver introduces an extra parameter: the precision that needs to be reached in the iteration process. This parameter can be used to trade speed for precision; the optimal setting is found to be around $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$, or 5 digits. The quantification of the uncertainty attributable to this parameter, and other model settings, has been published in Jansson et al. (2021).

The total runtime performance of DALES has been improved by approximately 30% (see the plot on the right in Figure 2). Further optimisations that we have introduced include:

Figure 2: Scaling of DALES using the FFT-based solver for the pressure equation and the new multi-grid iterative method.

- Restructure loops to improve autovectorisation of code hotspots;
- Decrease the halo-exchanged data by excluding microphysical quantities which are not needed by neighbouring processors;
- Decrease MPI all-to-all communication by reimplementing the matrix transposes; needed for the Fourier transforms;
- Use the FFTW library instead of a custom code;
- Refactor the microphysics module to reduce memory allocation and copying;
- Add checks to the advection and diffusion schemes to only run where necessary;
- overall code quality and maintainability improvements.

Both the new iterative solver and the FFT-based solver can make use of hardware acceleration (CUDA) through the HYPRE library, although this is still in early development and has not been tested yet for DALES. Of additional interest is the possibility of non-periodic boundary conditions and complex terrain when using the iterative solver. Finally, we have set up an experimental version of the single-precision DALES with the u, v, w prognostic fields being represented by 32-bit floats. After minor adaptations to the numerics, acceptable vertical profiles were observed as well as a 7% speedup of the RICO case.

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale There are about 10 more prognostic fields that could be reduced to single precision. Additionally, parts of the code (the iterative poisson solver, the cloud microdynamics, and the chemistry modules) can probably be used with single precision. This seems an encouraging path towards an even better-performing and better scalable version of DALES.

4.2.3 EMAC

The ECHAM/MESSy Atmospheric Chemistry (EMAC) model is a numerical chemistry and climate simulation system that includes sub-models describing tropospheric and middle atmosphere processes and their interaction with oceans, land and human influences (Jöckel et al., 2010). It uses the second version of the Modular Earth Submodel System (MESSy2) to link multi-institutional computer codes. The core atmospheric model is the 5th generation European Centre Hamburg general circulation model (ECHAM5) (Roeckner et al., 2006).

The acceleration of atmospheric chemical kinetics (Christoudias and Alvanos, 2016) and refactoring for new technologies (such as GPU accelerators) can reduce the required CPU-nodes and time-to-solution by a factor of 5–10 (Alvanos and Christoudias, 2017), with an order of magnitude more complex atmospheric chemical mechanism (in terms of number of species and reactions) compared to the current state-of-the-art, towards enabling Exascale performance (Alvanos and Christoudias, 2019). Indeed, in EMAC, a source-to-source compiler outputs a CUDA-compatible kernel by parsing the FORTRAN code generated by the Kinetic PreProcessor (KPP) general analysis tool. All Rosenbrock methods that are available in the KPP numerical library are supported.

The goal of our work was to reduce the memory footprint of the code in the device code (i.e. GPU), and as such allow more MPI tasks to be concurrently run on the same hardware. This allowed to:

1. Optimise performance for current and future GPU technologies, including NVIDIA Volta GPU and later, and
2. Extend computational capability to be able to handle an order of magnitude more complex chemistry, such as the Mainz Organic Mechanism (MOM) (Sander et al., 2019).

EMAC is a distributed memory application comprising:

- A non-local dynamical (spectral) part with low scalability, exclusively relying on the Message Passing Interface (MPI) for parallelisation.
- Local physical/chemical processes that can be massively parallelised with high scalability, ported on GPU architectures using the MEDINA (MECCA Development in Accelerators) code-to-code parser.

The EMAC MECCA sub-model (Sander et al., 2019) numerically solves the ordinary differential equations (ODEs) describing atmospheric chemical kinetics. In typical climate simulations, chemical kinetics can take up to 90% of the execution time. Each CPU process that offloads to the GPU requires a chunk of the GPU VRAM memory, whose size depends on the number of species and reaction constants in the MECCA mechanism. The number of GPUs per node and VRAM memory available in each GPU dictates the total number of CPU processes that can run concurrently.

Stack frame memory or local memory is allocated for all available threads of the GPU. For example, a V100 accelerator has 2048 active threads per streaming multiprocessor (SM) and 80 SMs, so at runtime the kernel will allocate a total of $2048 \times 80 \times (\text{size of local memory})$ Bytes in the VRAM of the GPU. Thus for the same code and problem size the total stack memory requirement is higher for newer generation GPUs, as they have more SM units and more active threads per SM. For instance, a K40 employs a maximum of

2048 active threads in 15 SMs (compared to 80 SMs in V100). However, as stack memory is allocated for the maximum number of threads a GPU could run concurrently, the GPU quickly runs out of memory when multiple processes are offloading work to the GPU simultaneously.

To alleviate the stack memory overflow issues and improve overall performance of the GPU computational kernel we have implemented the following optimisations:

- Use heap memory in numerical solvers for stiff ODEs
- Move chemical reaction constants from stack to global memory
- Transfer tracer concentration arrays to global memory
- Use direct pointer indexing for array memory access
- Use streams to overlap computation with device to-and-from memory transfers

Alternatively, the NVIDIA Multi-Process Service (MPS) can be used to force each process launching a kernel on a GPU to use only a part of the available threads, which limits the total memory requirement of MPI processes per node offloading to the same GPU. In our tests, setting the CUDA MPS active thread percentage to 10% in our runtime environment allowed us to run with ten times more processes per GPU, thus keeping the CPU thread count high on each individual compute node for better balancing the CPU/GPU application component. However, we regard using this setting as a workaround rather than a sustainable solution. The MPS can be used without the “active thread percentage” variable which still allows kernel and memcpy operations from different processes to overlap on the GPU, achieving higher utilisation and shorter running times according to NVIDIA.

The results presented in this work were obtained on a benchmark representative of a real-world application, simulating 1 model month at 15 min timesteps with 142 chemical species, 310 chemical reactions, $128 \times 64 \times 31 = 253952$ gridpoints (longitude, latitude, vertical levels respectively) – at a spherical truncation of T42 (corresponding to a quadratic Gaussian grid of $\sim 2.8 \times 2.8^\circ$ in latitude and longitude) and using the Rosenbrock 3-step implicit Runge–Kutta numerical integrator.

The results presented in this work have been obtained on an Atos BullSequana XH2000 supercomputer equipped with compute nodes having the following specifications: $2 \times$ Intel Skylake Xeon 6148 (20 cores @ 2.4 GHz), $4 \times$ NVIDIA Tesla V100 32GB SXM2, 394 GB RAM DDR4 2667 MT/s.

Code Version	Time to solution (s)	Speedup
Original reference (16 MPI processes/node = maximum possible)	13504.0	1 \times
Optimised w/o MPS (40 MPI processes/node)	7674.3	1.76 \times
Optimised w/ MPS (40 MPI processes/node)	7401.9	1.82 \times

Table 2: Time to solution for the benchmark one-month simulation of the original reference implementation that could only use 16 MPI processes per compute node, and the optimised version including all memory optimisations that can now take advantage of up to 40 MPI processes (one per physical processor core). Note that using NVIDIA Multi-Process-Service (MPS) but without setting the active thread percentage achieves the best time to solution.

The achieved performance after these optimisations in terms of *i*) runtime and *ii*) required memory is presented in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively.

Optimisation	GPU Memory use per MPI Process (MiB)		
	Nominal	MPS	MPS +ATP=10%
Reference	7655	7653	801
+ Global reaction constants and all kernel arrays global	2313	2311	415
+ Pointer direct indexing	1549	1549	335

Table 3: Memory use for the benchmark one-month simulation with different optimisations. Achieved memory reduction by at least order five between reference and with all optimisations. (Note: the active thread percentage ATP at 10% does not produce a required memory reduction by a factor of 10.)

As a result of our optimisations, it is now possible to use 40 MPI processes (one process by core, 10 processes per GPU) per node concurrently to get the best time to solution compared to a maximum possible of 16 MPI processes originally, allowing $1.82\times$ overall speedup at node level. This is without using the MPS active thread percentage feature, which leads to a more efficient and future-proof code.

The overall speedup offered by the use of CUDA streams is not significant on V100 as it is constrained here by the size of the chemical ODE system, and it is still ongoing work.

To avoid memory issues when offloading a code to the GPU, application developers can opt as best practice instead of allocating local arrays in stack frame memory to rather allocate arrays in the GPU global memory.

Thanks to the proposed optimisations, the MECCA - KPP Fortran to CUDA source-to-source pre-processor has been improved. This new parser and CUDA Rosenbrock family implicit ODE solvers code can be used by other researchers to transform chemistry kinetics packages to CUDA-accelerated code. The methodology can be used as a template for creating high performance computing capabilities on GPUs for atmospheric modelling. The code is available on Github⁵ under the open source MIT license.

This work has been published at HPC Asia 2021 (Christoudias et al., 2021).

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale To move forward towards exascale, several tracks have been already identified and implemented, such as reducing the floating-point precision of data structures in the chemical kinetics solvers and improving the vectorisation (Sophocleous and Christoudias, 2022).

4.2.4 OBLIMAP2

OBLIMAP-2.0 (Reerink et al., 2016) is a fast, distributed climate–ice sheet model coupling code that includes online embeddable mapping routines. It can be used to evaluate atmospheric forcings and geothermal heat fluxes upon an ice sheet, allowing intermediate coordinate system projections between these data sources.

OBLIMAP-2.0 code uses a mapping technique for exchanging climate fields between a Global Circulation Model (GCM) and an Ice Sheet Model (ISM). The first step is a scan phase where the points of the output grid are placed in the input grid. The second phase is the mapping phase where the field values are mapped using the interpolation data from the scan phase.

First of all, a first profiling has been done on the test cases indicated by the OBLIMAP developer we collaborate with. One corresponds to Greenland (oblimap-ice2sea-to-im-greenland) at 2x2km and 20x20km resolution and the second one corresponds to Antarctica (oblimap-bedmap2-to-im-antarctica) at 20x20km

⁵<https://github.com/CyprusInst/medina>

resolution. These test cases have been processed using two different scan methods: the fast scan method and the full scan method. Note that when using a fast scan method, it may be necessary to fall back to the full scan method in some cases. For our experiments, the full scan method has not been applied on Antarctica to avoid very long execution time (several days).

The very first parallel version of OBLIMAP-2.0 has introduced a parallelisation with the MPI library in a way that only the scan phase loop has been split amongst the MPI processes. The main drawback of this approach is the memory consumption, as each MPI process allocates the full memory size of the problem. This duplication of memory rapidly saturates the available memory, especially on a large test case such as Antarctica 20x20km.

The goal of the service project is firstly to reduce the memory footprint of the code by improving its distribution over parallel tasks, and secondly resolve the I/O bottleneck by implementing parallel NetCDF reading and writing. This will improve the intra node scaling of OBLIMAP-2.0 by using all the cores of a node. A second step will be to extend the parallelisation scheme to support inter node execution. This work will establish OBLIMAP-2.0 as a candidate ice coupling library for large-scale, high-resolution climate models.

A first optimisation after analysing the source code consists of interchanging the loops to ensure that the elements in the processed arrays are accessed in the same order as organised in the memory to improve data locality, thus improving performance.

MPI Shared Memory has been introduced in the source code to avoid this memory duplication by each MPI process when running on the same compute node, i.e. when they can share the memory of a compute node. Each MPI process allocates its own arrays corresponding to a slice of the global array, and each process can read from the memory of other processes when executed on the same compute node.

In this way, each MPI process reads and writes only the data it needs, I/O can be done in parallel or to avoid saturating the file system bandwidth only the root MPI process read and write the data. This has been introduced in the source code using parallel NetCDF. As parallel NetCDF requires parallel HDF5 and NC4 format, a conversion is needed before the execution, and maybe afterwards for compliance with other processing tools. This can be removed if this newer input and output data format can be adopted by the OBLIMAP-2.0 users.

In order to support multi-node execution, i.e. supporting both shared and distributed memory execution models, a new level of domain decomposition has been introduced corresponding to "Global → Node → Process" instead of "Global → Process". As a first implementation approach, the global arrays are duplicated for each node. This means that the data must be allocated, read and written on a node basis in parallel (each root MPI process per node or by all processes). This also means that the memory is duplicated amongst the nodes.

The results presented in this document have been obtained on an Atos BullSequana XH2000 supercomputer equipped with two types of compute nodes having the following specifications: (i) BullSequana X2410 AMD blades with 2x CPU AMD "Rome" 7742 (64 cores @ 2.25 GHz), 256GB RAM DDR4 3200 MT/s memory and HDR 100 interconnect, (ii) BullSequana X2210 Xeon blades with 2x CPU Intel Xeon 6248 (20 cores @ 2.5 GHz), 187GB RAM DDR4 2933 MT/s memory and HDR 100 interconnect.

As one can see in Figure 3, the original MPI version memory consumption increases with the number of MPI processes, which prevents execution on the full node for the Antarctica test case, i.e. using 128 cores. A bug has been found and fixed, allowing to run the code with more than 16 MPI processes. Thanks to the integration of MPI shared memory in the code, the optimised version keeps the same memory consumption up to 8 MPI processes and then increases linearly. This behaviour is still under investigation, but a first guess is that some arrays not shared still need to be duplicated when reaching a certain level of parallelism. On an Intel CSL node we observed the same behaviour as with the AMD ROME, as the code is able to use all 40

Figure 3: OBLIMAP-2.0 fast scan memory consumption optimisation according to the number of MPI processes on one AMD ROME compute node.

Figure 4: OBLIMAP-2.0 full scan memory time to solution optimisation according to the number of MPI processes on one (top) and several (down) AMD ROME compute nodes.

cores in the node for both test cases. The results presented on these two figures have been obtained with the fast scan method but we obtained overall the same results with the full scan method.

Regarding the time to solution and the OBLIMAP-2.0 scalability, we present in Figure 4 (top) the full scan results on both the Greenland 20x20km and 2x2km test cases on one node (as the Antarctica test case run is very long with this full scan method). We obtained a speedup around 2.5x and 1.6x mainly thanks to the loop optimisation (loops interchange) on 20x20km and 2x2km respectively. Figure 4 (bottom) gives, in addition, the time to solution for multi-node execution. We can see that the code scales with a total speedup equal to 4.4x between the original code that was able to run only on a full node (taking advantage however to the bug fix presented before) and the optimised code that can now run on 4 nodes. Note that we cannot run

Figure 5: OBLIMAP-2.0 fast scan time to solution optimisation according to the number of MPI processes both AMD ROME and Intel CSL compute node.

the Greenland 20x20km testcase with more than 64 cores as there are not enough points in the X dimension to parallelise the computations, same with 2x2km with more than 4 nodes.

For the fast scan method, the scalability is not as good as for the full scan method as shown in Figure 5. This is due to the sequential part of the code that takes a larger place in the OBLIMAP-2.0 execution for this fast scan method. Nevertheless, one can see that the optimised version offers a speedup on the Antarctica test case between 1.5x and 2x on AMD ROME node and between 1.6x and 2.5x on Intel CSL node, on the Greenland test case between 1.1x and 1.9x on AMD ROME node and between 1.2x and 2x on Intel CSL node.

All the goals have been achieved: reducing the memory footprint with MPI shared memory, I/O and inter node parallel scheme implementation. This paves the way for establishing OBLIMAP-2.0 as a candidate ice coupling library for large-scale, high-resolution climate models.

This work has been presented at the European Geosciences Union (EGU) (Raffin et al., 2021).

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale To go further, we believe that distributing the grids on the processes with some overlapping, and introducing a new data structure (like a tree, for example) will help to quickly find the interpolation points in parallel. This will lead to a full parallelisation, which opens the doors to higher efficiency and better scalability. A GPU port may also be interesting.

4.2.5 AGRIF

AGRIF (Adaptive Grid Refinement In Fortran) is a package for the integration of full adaptive mesh refinement features within a multidimensional finite difference model. This library is used in ocean models like NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean) to offer the possibility to run multiple levels and 2-way nested embedded zooms. Within the ESiWACE2 project, AGRIF performance has been addressed toward high resolution simulations.

First, a simple AGRIF configuration within NEMO was set up to simplify benchmarking, profiling and testing new optimisations ideas. We selected on purpose a configuration with small MPI subdomains to mimic simulations running on high numbers of cores.

Second, a first profiling analysis has let us identify an important overhead. Indeed, in a zoom with a

refinement of a factor 3 in both latitude and longitude covering 1/9 of the simulated domain, an overhead of around 60% has been observed compared with the theoretical performance. The lower resolution zoom level values are used, after an interpolation, as forcing to be fed on the boundaries of the higher resolution zoom level. The correction applied when encountering land points in the interpolation has been found to be a major bottleneck thanks to a detailed profiling.

Third, we implemented an optimisation concerning the correction on land points limiting as much as possible the search for close-by ocean points by taking advantage of the specificity of each interpolation. In few words, the idea is to adapt the size of the search window whenever a land point is present instead of using an arbitrary size.

Moreover, a global communication used to collect information on the position of the higher resolution level has been removed in all situations but one: when a higher resolution level domain is moving inside lower resolution level (a rarely used functionality). Table 4 presents the percentage of run-time between reference and optimised version of the corresponding AGRIF routines. *CorrectnD* is the main AGRIF routine that is calling all other routines involved in the management of the different zoom levels, *Interpolation*, as its name suggests, is computing the interpolation between zoom levels, and *Checkmask* is called by *Interpolation* and handles the correction of land points. As one can see, the time spent in these routines has been decreased significantly.

% of runtime	Reference	Optimised
CorrectnD	29%	9%
Interpolation	20%	6%
Checkmask	11%	1.5%

Table 4: AGRIF optimisation results per routines.

These optimisations led to limiting the overhead to 20% instead of 60% in the aforementioned configuration as depicted in Figure 6. These initial results have been obtained on the SKL Irene partition of the TGCC Joliot Curie supercomputer⁶, a BullSequana X1000 equipped with Intel Skylake 8168. Latest experimentation on a more recent platform, a BullSequana XH2000 equipped with Intel Ice Lake based compute nodes, has shown that the AGRIF performance and the proposed optimisation have a different behaviour while still remaining beneficial, see Figure 7.

AGRIF allows to simulate selected parts of the Ocean with higher precision, but its cost in terms of runtime has led to a restricted use. Thanks to the optimisations performed and envisioned in the project, a wider adoption of AGRIF is possible to move forward its use at large scale in global simulations.

This work has been presented at the European Geosciences Union (EGU) (Irrmann et al., 2022).

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale Higher performance will be possible with the implementation of new identified optimisations, including the correction of land points. Load balancing has also been identified as a potential issue and should be addressed to move forward and advance this code towards exascale.

4.2.6 RTE+RRTMGP-CPP

Overview: The Rapid Radiative Transfer Model for GCM applications (RRTMG) is one of the most widely adopted radiation physics packages throughout the field of atmospheric physics and climate modelling. The successor of RRTMG adopts a more flexible, object-oriented programming interface and balances accuracy

⁶<https://www-hpc.cea.fr/en/complexe/tgcc-JoliotCurie.htm>

Figure 6: AGRIF reduced overhead from 60% to 20% on global time to solution on an Intel Skylake 8168 based platform.

Figure 7: AGRIF reduced overhead from 71% to 41% on global time to solution on a more recent platform equipped with Intel Ice Lake 8358 CPUs.

and efficiency in the Radiative Transfer for Energetics (RTE) and RRTM for GCM applications—Parallel (RTE+RRTMGP) library. RTE+RRTMGP-CPP is the C++ interface and CUDA port of RRTMGP, which is currently being developed by the group of Chiel van Heerwaarden at Wageningen University and Research.

The first goal is to improve application performance by removing the overhead from repeated GPU memory management operations. Furthermore, the current CUDA kernel code needs to be optimised to improve the memory bandwidth utilisation and parallelism. Finally, we plan to tune the compute kernels and their parallel layout in a systematic and automated way.

The original C++ code had many repeated GPU memory allocations, hampering GPU performance. These allocations were only for temporary arrays. The non-temporary arrays were indeed allocated at initialisation and used throughout the execution. The temporary arrays were, however, so large and numerous that the application would not have been able to execute on most GPUs. We have replaced these with CUDA-native pool allocations, or alternatively, a self-written pool class. This way we have gained an order of magnitude in performance while keeping memory usage within limits.

In addition, we have used a two-stage approach to optimising the performance of the GPU kernels in the code. First, we have used an independent sandbox-like approach using Kernel Tuner(van Werkhoven, 2019) to create optimised and tuned implementations for many of the GPU kernels. The code optimisations that were introduced include fusing kernels, reordering, fusing or splitting loops, recomputing values (e.g. to avoid the need for loads and stores in temporary arrays). Many of these optimisations have in turn reduced the need for many, but not all, of the temporary arrays stored in GPU device memory. We have also changed the order of dimensions in the parallelisation and the way certain dimensions were mapped to threads and thread blocks in several kernels. We have changed the code to precompute certain values on the CPU instead of redundantly on the GPU. We also reduced register usage in some kernels by replacing kernel arguments with template arguments, or limiting loop unrolling by tuning the partial loop unrolling factor. Whether or not to use most of these optimisations can be auto-tuned in combination with execution parameters such as the thread block dimensions to arrive at very fast implementations.

Secondly, we have used an online, integrated approach looping automatically over the kernel configuration space to find the best parallel launch parameters at runtime during initialisation of the application. The result of our optimisations and tuning the individual kernels combined yields another order of magnitude in performance improvement.

We have established a significant leap in performance for RTE+RRTMGP-CPP using the above optimisation techniques. The resulting GPU code is over 200 times faster than the single-threaded CPU version of RTE+RRTMGP-CPP. A multithreaded version of the CPU application does not exist at time of writing. However, it is important to note that multiple cores in a CPU can be used when the radiation code is embedded in a larger parallel application. In comparison with the original Fortran code (RTE+RRTMGP), we observe well over 200x speed-up and over 1.7x better performance of the OpenACC-accelerated original code. We are currently working towards integrating the tuned GPU kernels into the original RTE+RRTMGP source code as a new accelerated back-end.

This work has been presented at the American Geophysical Union (AGU) 2021 (van den Oord et al., 2021).

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale The radiation transfer library RTE+RRTMGP-CPP has been extensively tuned and optimised, and is fit for purpose in large-scale, CUDA-accelerated HPC applications. However, changes in the number of vertical layers, the number of spectral bands, or other physical quantities may require a re-tuning of its kernels. Similarly, deploying the code onto different future accelerator architectures requires re-calibration as well. Therefore, to ensure performance portability across exascale architectures, as next steps we propose to integrate a system for and storing and

reading tuned parameters in RTE+RRTMGP-CPP.

4.2.7 BLOM

In this project, we have exploited the performance of the global ocean code BLOM (Bergen Layered Ocean Model) on a hybrid platform (i.e. MPI+OpenMP). Initially, MPI+OpenMP was under-performing in comparison to MPI, at least on 4 OpenMP threads. But after a few changes, we were able to reach a stage where MPI+OpenMP was a better choice than MPI only. This opens up further possibilities to use more efficiently CPU-cores on existing hardware and achieve a better throughput by avoiding halo exchange or copies.

Thanks to this collaboration, the BLOM team modified the computationally expensive parts of the code (representing 30-40% of the total execution time) suggested by the ESiWACE team. The BLOM team implemented some of the suggestions and a few have been kept on hold because they would take a long time to implement.

Now, BLOM has better performance on a hybrid programming architecture (MPI+OpenMP) than MPI only. With further implementations of these suggestions in the remaining part of the code, we could expect a much better performance.

In tables 5 and 6 we present performance results with optimised code obtained on the Betzy supercomputer⁷, which is a BullSequana XH2000 equipped with AMD 7742 CPUs. The following three optimisations have been tested: a) CPU binding of OpenMP threads b) loop restructuring c) uses of collapse directives. Loop restructuring optimisations consist in (i) reordering the iterations to access the memory continuously and (ii) introducing full loops (i.e. iterating on the whole domain space) with one if to avoid land points instead of segmented loops (iterating only on ocean points). Lastly, the collapse directive has proven to be quite beneficial.

MPI tasks	timing (s)	MPI tasks × OpenMP threads	timing (s)
128	65	8×16	81
		16×8	72
		32×4	57
		64×2	58

Table 5: Node level performance of optimised code: MPI Vs OpenMP for small test case

The best performance is achieved on 4 OpenMP threads with 32 MPI tasks, which is 57 seconds; that is around 12% better than only 128 MPI tasks.

MPI tasks	timing (s)	MPI tasks × OpenMP threads	timing (s)	MPI tasks × OpenMP threads	timing (s)
256	355				
512	177	256×2	171		
1024	107	256×4	103	512×2	98
2048	77	256×8	79	512×4	64

Table 6: Performance of optimised code: MPI Vs OpenMP for large test case

Table 6 presents MPI Vs MPI+OpenMP performance for large channel setup. We mostly notice that hybrid code was performing better than MPI only code.

⁷https://documentation.sigma2.no/hpc_machines/betzy.html

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale: Our first step would be to implement all suggested changes to the whole BLOM code and also then to apply these changes to the HAMOCC code (Global ocean biogeochemistry model - part of the BLOM code).

In a second step we will consider the maintainability of the scientific code while introducing different directives (OpenMP, OpenACC). A methodology has been presented to the BLOM team on this aspect.

4.2.8 OGSTM

The OGSTM (Transport Model of the "Istituto di Oceanografia e Geofisica Sperimentale") and BFM (Biogeochemical Flux Model) coupled model is the main component of a fully automatic system that delivers, since 2007, weekly analyses and forecast maps for the Mediterranean Sea biogeochemistry in the framework of the EU Copernicus Marine Service⁸.

The transfer of the model to GPU technology would be strategic to exploit novel exascale clusters therefore increasing the performance of the code to perform ensemble forecasts and faster climate scenario studies. Usually solving the transport of complex marine biogeochemical models with a high number of tracers (BFM has 50+ tracers) is known to be a heavy computational task. OGSTM-BFM is optimised to perform this on CPU architectures but the upgrade to GPU is essential for current and next generation clusters used by OGS⁹. Model profiling has confirmed the role of transport in determining the time-to-solution. Therefore, the porting of the OGSTM-BFM transport operator to the GPU architecture has been addressed. The profiling indicates that also the BFM biogeochemical reactor in OGSTM-BFM plays a relevant role. Consequently, the porting of BFM to GPU architecture has been studied.

BFM performance: Out of the 4 main routines of BFM only mesoZooDynamics was ported to GPU and its single core performance is presented in Table 7. The CPU performance of the routine is fairly degraded by the batching process developed during the project to extract more parallelism from this part. The GPU speedup on the kernels is only 10.7, which is low compared to a single CPU core, but an encouraging start.

Version	MesoZoo Transfers (s)	MesoZoo Kernels (s)	MesoZoo Total (s)	BFM step (s)
CPU old	0	6.89	6.89	69.71
CPU batched	0	18.93	18.93	130.2
GPU	2.36	0.643 (x10.7)	3.0 (x2.3)	114.0
GPU pinned	1.03	0.642 (x10.7)	1.67 (x4.1)	110.7

Table 7: Single core 2 hours simulation timing of the MesoZoo routine.

Current data layout is suboptimal. As such, we observe on the GPU kernel of Table 8 a speedup of about 16 compared to the non-coalesced GPU version. The same order of speedup could be achieved on many other kernels in mesoZooDynamics because they are all similarly structured. This also applies to all other routines in BFM, and significant gain could also be obtained for CPU execution. This should be the first point of focus in the future. It was not implemented because BFM relies a lot on array operations where the dimension of both operands needs to match, and it is not easy to automatically do the swap. The signature of the aforementioned array as well as some code sections are also generated by a template system, complexifying the task.

⁸<https://marine.copernicus.eu/>

⁹Marconi100 and Leonardo

GPU Kernel version	Total (ns)	Average (ns)	Speedup
mem_flux_vector regular	391,676,353	430,413.6	1
mem_flux_vector coalesced	24,321,375	26,726.8	16.1

Table 8: Impact of coalesced GPU memory access by swapping array dimensions.

Time (s)	CPU	GPU	Speedup
Alloc	0.07	0.10	
Data transfers	0.00	0.80	
Kernel	15.78	0.40	39.44
Advection	15.74	1.31	12.01
TrcStep	63.36	49.37	1.28
Total	129.68	85.71	1.51

Table 9: Single core 2 hours simulation timing of the advection routine.

Data transfers between CPU memory and GPU memory reduce even more the speedup illustrated in Table 7. When porting the other BFM routines, the data transfer should not increase much. Most arrays are only used locally inside the routines, so we do not need to transfer their content to CPU, and the three main arrays used by all routines are already fully transferred back and forth. So we can expect data transfer to degrade the total speedup less and less, the more BFM routines are ported to GPU.

OGSTM performance: The performance of the advection routine for single core execution is presented in Table 9. We obtain a fairly good kernel speedup of about 39.4 diminished by the data transfer between CPU and GPU. Those data transfers could be reduced when porting more sections of OGSTM. As for the allocations, they could be moved to an initialisation phase and then removed from the iteration phase. However, the advection is only a part of the tracer step (TrcStep) and it becomes more apparent after optimising it that we now need to focus on the rest of TrcStep.

First tests have been carried out on a multi-node configuration showing that more work needs to be done. By default, kernel(s) of different processes cannot run simultaneously on the same GPU, they are serialised. Also, switching between processes can be expensive. If we look at the data of Table 10 we can clearly see that the kernels have quite worse performance that we could expect. To work around these two issues, we recommend investigating the use of the CUDA Multi-Process Service (MPS¹⁰).

There is another factor in play, which is related to the MPI communications. From Table 10 we see that on CPUs, MPI communication (including packing) will take less than a second in total. On GPUs, using GPU-aware MPI, the performance is quite drastically worse. By having 5 ranks per GPU we are increasing the pressure on GPU-CPU bandwidth, but most importantly, it is probably the sheer number of GPU-aware data transfers that limits throughput. In the current version, the MPI communications are done using GPU-aware MPI. We recommend trying different methods such as transferring data manually between CPU and GPU and doing the MPI communications normally.

The last key factor is related to the domain decomposition and work imbalance. The workload depends greatly on whether a subdomain contains land grid points (which implies no computation) or only ocean grid points. It is highly likely that we have several work-intensive ranks sharing the same GPU, while at the same time having some ranks with less workload barely using a GPU. We recommend investigating different configurations with a lower number of processes per GPU, trying different dispatching techniques of the ranks to even the workload or trying more advanced domain decomposition methods.

¹⁰https://docs.nvidia.com/deploy/pdf/CUDA_Multi_Process_Service_Overview.pdf

Time (s)	CPU			GPU		
	min	max	avg	min	max	avg
Alloc	0.1	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.30	0.20
Barrier	0.7	24.00	16.30	1.10	55.50	27.90
Comm (MPI+pack)	0.3	0.70	0.60	9.20	31.70	20.20
Comm (MPI)	0.3	0.50	0.40	4.70	17.10	11.80
Comm (pack)	0	0.30	0.20	0.10	16.30	8.40
Data transfers	0	0.00	0.00	2.70	4.70	4.10
Kernel	12.9	14.40	13.70	1.30	17.50	11.60

Table 10: 97 cores 2 hours simulation detailed timing of the advection routine.

Time Avg (s)	CPU	GPU	Speedup
Advection	30.46	63.46	0.48
TrcStep	67.86	101.64	0.67
Total	127.50	150.61	0.85

Table 11: 97 cores 2 hours simulation summarised timing of the advection routine.

Synthesis: During this project we have finally identified how to transform the OGSTM-BFM application to be able to exploit GPU architecture to be prepared for exascale computing. We undertook work to massively increase parallelism in BFM, and have laid the foundation needed to exploit this parallelism fully. Using OpenACC directives, we believe the developers will be able to maintain and extend the porting effort to execute the whole BFM and OGSTM code on a GPU architecture.

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale: The exascale challenge will drive the evolution of the OGSTM-BFM code, and more generally of the whole MedBFM model system.

As suggested by the HPC experts during the project, the model will definitely require efficient use of GPU architectures:

- 1) to improve the load balancing among MPI ranks by investigating different strategies for domain decomposition;
- 2) to extend the coalesced GPU version by swapping the dimensions of arrays for the highest number of BFM routines;
- 3) to investigate MPI communication patterns, starting with manual/controlled data transfer between CPU and GPU;
- 4) to investigate the use of optimised libraries to perform the same operations / algorithms but more efficiently.

4.2.9 RegCM

The REGIONal Climate Model (RegCM) is a state-of-the-art limited area model, developed by the Earth System Physics section of the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) for long-term regional climate simulation. It has been used in numerous regional model inter-comparison projects to produce climate projections for the next century by the process of physical downscaling of the output of Global Climate Models that are part of the the World Climate Research Programme's (WCRP) Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP).

The model code version control is maintained using Git and publicly hosted on GitHub¹¹.

The project objective of ESiWACE2 service 1 for RegCM was to port part of the Regional Climate model code, which uses a 2D Cartesian horizontal decomposition, to a GPU cluster using OpenACC and CUDA-aware MPI. Specifically, the main target of the porting effort was the newest dynamical core of the model, with the possibility to accelerate also part of the 1D physical parameterisation packages.

The capability to accelerate the model execution using GPUs will open up the road for the RegCM user community to evaluate future climate extremes that are expected to change over multiple high-resolution domains all over the world, in particular in high-threat areas for climate change such as the Indo-Gangetic plane, Southern Europe, the Sahel Region and the la Plata basin. The 3km resolution can provide useful information on future extremes in temperature and precipitation serving as red flag warnings for possible life-disruptive changes in spot regions around the globe. Currently, this is the target of multiple pilot studies.

Porting a sizeable part of the code to the GPU could later be used as a blueprint to extend the porting to the whole code-base. The capability to accelerate the code using a GPU cluster is seen as mandatory by the RegCM developers for accessing current and near-future HPC platforms.

An initial performance analysis has been conducted on the two provided test cases: (i) a low resolution European domain at 50km horizontal resolution (ii) a high resolution at 3km over the Alpine region representative of a future setting for which the GPU clusters would be the target platform to obtain the level of compute performance that would make the scientific project targets viable. Based on the obtained results, it was decided to begin the effort with porting the non-hydrostatic dynamical core of RegCM to GPUs using OpenACC. At a later stage, the focus would shift towards the physical parameterisations, with the radiation and cloud microphysics as obvious candidates for GPU acceleration.

Then, several steps have been necessary to port the non-hydrostatic dynamical core:

- Increasing parallelism by introducing algorithmic changes to the advection loops;
- Asynchronous data transfers to mitigate the performance penalty induced by data transfers between device and host; this allows overlapping some host and device processing methods with the copying of arrays.

With the full non-hydrostatic dynamical core of RegCM ported to GPUs using OpenACC, we see promising speedups on the Juwels-Booster machine. Unfortunately, these improvements decrease towards higher node counts, where realistic production-level climate simulations would benefit most. This is due to the fact that (i) the current port is predominantly a straightforward insertion of OpenACC directives with only a handful of optimisations at the source code level, and (ii) the abundant MPI communication within the dynamical core limits the scalability of the application with the number of available GPUs, and (iii) the balance between CPU and GPU performance in the machine. However, at the time of writing this project is still running. Preliminary performance tests on the Marconi 100 have shown a speedup of 2x over the CPU-only version and importantly, sustained improvement towards higher node counts.

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale Looking forward, we identify three main routes towards better utilisation of the available compute resources. Firstly, the acceleration of physics parameterisations will enable a speedup of realistic climate simulations involving radiation, clouds, convection and the surface scheme. This may create the opportunity to increase the number of calls to the radiative transfer code, improving model accuracy. Secondly, optimising the loops and data layouts and possibly performance-tuning the OpenACC kernels are expected to greatly improve the performance of the

¹¹<https://github.com/ICTP/RegCM>

GPU-resident dynamical core. Finally, optimising the MPI communication could benefit RegCM on both GPU clusters as well as traditional higher-tier HPC systems.

4.2.10 MicroHH

MicroHH (van Heerwaarden et al., 2017) is an open-source computational fluid dynamics code for direct numerical simulation (DNS) and large-eddy simulation (LES) of atmospheric turbulent flows. Compared to current numerical weather prediction (NWP) models, LES does not rely on physical parameterisations for turbulence and clouds. Instead, it explicitly resolves the largest turbulent eddies by using a fine horizontal resolution of $\mathcal{O}(1\text{-}100\text{ m})$. This can reduce the uncertainty related to e.g. clouds and precipitation, and hence improve the quality of weather forecasts. Over the last few years, MicroHH has been extended with various physics parameterisations necessary to simulate realistic weather. This includes the RTE-RRTMGP radiative transfer model (Pincus et al., 2019), a single-moment ice microphysics scheme (Tomita, 2008), and an interactive land-surface model (Balsamo et al., 2009). As such, the model can now be used to explore the benefits and limitations of using LES for weather predictions.

MicroHH can run fully on both the CPU (C++) and GPU (CUDA-C++), but the GPU version had some limitations. The porting of CPU code to GPU kernels was done in a somewhat naive way, mostly replacing the CPU `for` loops by CUDA thread-based indexing, without much further CUDA-specific optimisations. Furthermore, the GPU version only supports the use of a single GPU.

The goal of this ESiWACE2 service project was twofold. Firstly, the main aim was to optimise the existing GPU code using the Kernel Launcher and Kernel Tuner (van Werkhoven, 2019) software development tools developed by NLeSC. Secondly, this project has explored the possibility to extend MicroHH to a multi-GPU setup.

In the GPU version we have chosen to port all code from the main time loop to the GPU. This way, memory transfers between the host and GPU are only required during the computation of time-integrated statistics and/or I/O time steps. The initial GPU port did not contain any GPU-specific performance optimisations, for example *shared memory* on the GPU was only used when strictly necessary for correctness.

Initial performance analysis was carried out to evaluate the current performance of the application and to determine the most computationally expensive GPU kernels. The application was executed on an NVIDIA A100 GPU, a GPU targeted at HPC applications and based on the Ampere architecture, the latest GPU architecture by NVIDIA. This analysis led to the identification of four GPU kernels related to advection and three GPU kernels related to diffusion representing respectively 34% and roughly 32% of the total execution time. These seven GPU kernels together make up two thirds of the total execution time and will be the targets of performance optimisations.

The main kernel parameters identified that have an important impact on performance according to the test case (defined by the grid size and the use of single or double precision) are the following:

- Thread block size per kernel;
- Minimum number of resident thread blocks per streaming multiprocessor (SM);
- Number of processed grid points per thread.

To determine the optimal parameters for the seven kernels for different scenarios, we used *Kernel Tuner*¹². Kernel Tuner is a tool for testing, validating, and automatic tuning of GPU code. Kernel Tuner supports

¹²https://kerneltuner.github.io/kernel_tuner/

many different search optimisation algorithms and is capable of handling the large and discontinuous search spaces that are common in tuning GPU kernels. To integrate the tuning results of Kernel Tuner back into MicroHH, we used *Kernel Launcher* ¹³. Kernel Launcher is a C++ library that dynamically selects the optimal configuration for each kernel, compiles the CUDA kernel at runtime, and launches it on the GPU. This solution is future-proof since the kernels can easily be re-tuned for future GPU architectures.

Several kernels have also been optimised by rewriting their mathematical equations to use less expensive operations. For instance, it was found that the advection kernels perform divisions by the variable `rhoref`. Division of floating-point numbers is computationally expensive and, on GPUs, division can be an order of magnitude more expensive than multiplication. By precomputing the reciprocal of `rhoref` once during initialisation, this division could be converted into a multiplication. Another notable example is `evisc_g` where equations could be expressed differently, which enabled us to remove 4 divisions and 2 `pow` function calls per grid point.

To evaluate the performance of the optimised kernels, we consider the `drycb11es` use case for two grid sizes: a small grid of $256 \times 256 \times 256$ points and a larger grid of $512 \times 512 \times 512$ points. Additionally, we consider the kernels for both single precision (32 bit) and double precision (64 bit) floating-point accuracy. The GPU that we use is an NVIDIA Ampere A100, which has 40GB of device memory.

Figure 8 shows the relative speedup obtained thanks to the code optimisations. We observe that all kernels see a performance increase of at least 5% after optimisation. The performance improvements across all kernels are larger for single precision than for double precision accuracy. For instance, for a $512 \times 512 \times 512$ grid, the average improvement is 60% for single precision and 45% for double precision runs.

Most notable are the improvements for the kernels `diff_uvw` and `evisc`, where we see up to almost 200% increase in performance. The `diff_uvw` kernel uses a large number of intermediate values, thus careful tuning of the block size and the register usage leads to a large performance improvement. The `evisc` kernel uses various expensive mathematical operations (division, square root, power function), some of which could be removed by rewriting the equations, resulting in a noticeable performance improvement for double precision runs.

Finally, we present a run-time analysis for the complete application. These times include the execution time for the GPU, but also the time spent on auxiliary tasks such as reading inputs, writing results, calculating statistics, and transferring data between host and device memory. Figure 9 shows performance for the `drycb11es` case after 5000 time iterations. The figure shows that the performance increase is significant. For example, for double precision, the total run-time goes from around 35 minutes to less than 30 minutes. The overall decrease in run-time is 14% for double precision and 17% for single precision.

Discuss how to move forward and advance the code towards exascale The majority of supercomputers nowadays rely on GPUs of to provide high performance. For instance, the Frontier system ¹⁴, the first operational exascale system in the world, is capable of delivering its massive performance mainly thanks to its 37,888 GPUs. Optimising and tuning the performance of scientific applications for GPUs is thus important in moving towards exascale. With this work, we have brought MicroHH one step closer to the exascale era. In particular, we have automated the entire process of re-tuning and deploying the code onto different (future) accelerator architectures, ensuring performance portability across exascale architectures.

¹³https://kerneltuner.github.io/kernel_launcher/

¹⁴<https://www.top500.org/system/180047/>

Figure 8: Speedup of optimised kernels over baseline.

Figure 9: Run-time in minutes of full application for 5000 time iterations.

5 References

- Michail Alvanos and Theodoros Christoudias. GPU-accelerated atmospheric chemical kinetics in the ECHAM/MESSy (EMAC) Earth system model (version 2.52). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 10(10): 3679, 2017.
- Michail Alvanos and Theodoros Christoudias. Accelerating atmospheric chemical kinetics for climate simulations. *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, 30(11):2396–2407, 2019.
- Gianpaolo Balsamo, Anton Beljaars, Klaus Scipal, Pedro Viterbo, Bart van den Hurk, Martin Hirschi, and Alan K Betts. A revised hydrology for the ecmwf model: Verification from field site to terrestrial water storage and impact in the integrated forecast system. *jhm*, 10(3):623–643, 2009. doi: 10.1175/2008JHM1068.1.
- T. Christoudias, T. Kirfel, A. Kerkweg, D. Taraborrelli, G.-E. Moulard, E. Raffin, V. Azizi, G.V.D. Oord, and B.V. Werkhoven. GPU Optimizations for Atmospheric Chemical Kinetics. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, pages 136–138, 2021.
- Theodoros Christoudias and Michail Alvanos. Accelerated chemical kinetics in the emac chemistry-climate model. In *2016 International Conference on High Performance Computing & Simulation (HPCS)*, pages 886–889. IEEE, 2016.
- S. Danilov, D. Sidorenko, Q. Wang, and T. Jung. The finite-volume sea ice–ocean model (fesom2). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 10(2):765–789, 2017. doi: 10.5194/gmd-10-765-2017. URL <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/10/765/2017/>.
- Stijn Heldens, Pieter Hijma, Ben Van Werkhoven, Jason Maassen, Adam S. Z. Belloum, and Rob V. Van Nieuwpoort. The landscape of exascale research: A data-driven literature analysis. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 53(2), March 2020. ISSN 0360-0300. doi: 10.1145/3372390. URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3372390>.
- T. Heus, C. C. van Heerwaarden, H. J. J. Jonker, A. Pier Siebesma, S. Axelsen, K. van den Dries, O. Geoffroy, A. F. Moene, D. Pino, S. R. de Roode, and J. Vilà-Guerau de Arellano. Formulation of the dutch atmospheric large-eddy simulation (dales) and overview of its applications. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 3(2): 415–444, 2010. doi: 10.5194/gmd-3-415-2010. URL <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/3/415/2010/>.
- Gaston Irrmann, Sebastien Masson, Laurent Debreu, David Guibert, and Erwan Raffin. Optimizations of multiscale simulation with AGRIF, towards exascale applications. mar 2022. doi: 10.5194/egusphere-egu22-12292. URL <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-12292>.
- Fredrik Jansson, Wouter Edeling, Jisk Attema, and Daan Crommelin. Assessing uncertainties from physical parameters and modelling choices in an atmospheric large eddy simulation model. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A.*, 379, 2021. doi: 10.1098/rsta.2020.0073. URL <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0073>.
- Patrick Jöckel, Astrid Kerkweg, Andrea Pozzer, Rolf Sander, Holger Tost, Hella Riede, Andreas Baumgaertner, Sergey Gromov, and Bastian Kern. Development cycle 2 of the modular earth submodel system (messy2). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 3:717–752, 2010.
- N. V. Koldunov, V. Aizinger, N. Rakowsky, P. Scholz, D. Sidorenko, S. Danilov, and T. Jung. Scalability and some optimization of the finite-volume sea ice–ocean model, version 2.0 (fesom2). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(9):3991–4012, 2019. doi: 10.5194/gmd-12-3991-2019. URL <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/12/3991/2019/>.

- B. N. Lawrence, M. Rezny, R. Budich, P. Bauer, J. Behrens, M. Carter, W. Deconinck, R. Ford, C. Maynard, S. Mullerworth, C. Osuna, A. Porter, K. Serradell, S. Valcke, N. Wedi, and S. Wilson. Crossing the chasm: how to develop weather and climate models for next generation computers? *Geoscientific Model Development*, 11(5):1799–1821, 2018. doi: 10.5194/gmd-11-1799-2018. URL <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/11/1799/2018/>.
- A. Müller, W. Deconinck, C. Kühnlein, G. Mengaldo, M. Lange, N. Wedi, P. Bauer, P. K. Smolarkiewicz, M. Diamantakis, S.-J. Lock, M. Hamrud, S. Saarinen, G. Mozdzyński, D. Thiemert, M. Ginton, P. Bénard, F. Voitus, C. Colavolpe, P. Marguinaud, Y. Zheng, J. Van Bever, D. Degrauwe, G. Smet, P. Termonia, K. P. Nielsen, B. H. Sass, J. W. Poulsen, P. Berg, C. Osuna, O. Fuhrer, V. Clement, M. Baldauf, M. Gillard, J. Szmelter, E. O'Brien, A. McKinstry, O. Robinson, P. Shukla, M. Lysaght, M. Kulczewski, M. Ciznicki, W. Piatek, S. Ciesielski, M. Błażewicz, K. Kurowski, M. Procyk, P. Sychala, B. Bosak, Z. P. Piotrowski, A. Wyszogrodzki, E. Raffin, C. Mazauric, D. Guibert, L. Douriez, X. Vigouroux, A. Gray, P. Messmer, A. J. Macfaden, and N. New. The ESCAPE project: Energy-efficient Scalable Algorithms for Weather Prediction at Exascale. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(10):4425–4441, 2019. doi: 10.5194/gmd-12-4425-2019. URL <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/12/4425/2019/>.
- Robert Pincus, Eli J Mlawer, and Jennifer S Delamere. Balancing accuracy, efficiency, and flexibility in radiation calculations for dynamical models. *James*, 11(10):3074–3089, 2019. doi: 10.1029/2019MS001621.
- Erwan Raffin, David Guibert, and Thomas Reerink. OBLIMAP parallelization and optimization toward high resolution climate model - ice sheet model coupler. mar 2021. doi: 10.5194/egusphere-egu21-9880. URL <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-9880>.
- T. J. Reerink, W. J. van de Berg, and R. S. W. van de Wal. OBLIMAP 2.0: a fast climate model–ice sheet model coupler including online embeddable mapping routines. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9(11):4111–4132, 2016. doi: 10.5194/gmd-9-4111-2016. URL <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/9/4111/2016/>.
- E Roeckner, R Brokopf, M Esch, MA Giorgetta, S Hagemann, L Kornblueh, E Manzini, U Schlese, and U Schulzweida. Sensitivity of simulated climate to horizontal and vertical resolution in the echam5 atmosphere model. *Journal of Climate*, 19(16):3771–3791, 2006. doi: 10.1175/JCLI3824.1.
- R. Sander, A. Baumgaertner, D. Cabrera-Perez, F. Frank, S. Gromov, J.-U. Grooß, H. Harder, V. Huijnen, P. Jöckel, V. A. Karydis, K. E. Niemeyer, A. Pozzer, H. Riede, M. G. Schultz, D. Taraborrelli, and S. Tauer. The community atmospheric chemistry box model CAABA/MECCA-4.0. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(4):1365–1385, 2019. doi: 10.5194/gmd-12-1365-2019. URL <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/12/1365/2019/>.
- Kyriacos Sophocleous and Theo Christoudias. Reduced-precision chemical kinetics in atmospheric models. *Atmosphere*, 13:1418, 09 2022. doi: 10.3390/atmos13091418.
- Hirofumi Tomita. New microphysical schemes with five and six categories by diagnostic generation of cloud ice. *jmsj*, 86:121–142, 2008. doi: 10.2151/jmsj.86A.121.
- Gijs van den Oord, Alessio Sclocco, Georges-Emmanuel Moulard, David Guibert, Dmitry Sidorenko, Nikolay Koldunov, Ben van Werkhoven, Erwan Raffin, and Natalja Rakowski. GPU acceleration of the FESOM-2 ocean and sea-ice model. mar 2021. doi: 10.5194/egusphere-egu21-11551. URL <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-11551>.
- Gijs van den Oord, Alessio Sclocco, Bart van Stratum, Menno Veerman, Georges-Emmanuel Moulard, David Guibert, Erwan Raffin, Ben van Werkhoven, and Chiel van Heerwaarden. Optimization of RTE+RRTMGP-C++: a CUDA implementation of the radiation package RTE+RRTMGP for atmospheric science. In *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*, volume 2021, pages A55A–03, dec 2021.

Chiel C van Heerwaarden, Bart JH Van Stratum, Thijs Heus, Jeremy A Gibbs, Evgeni Fedorovich, and Juan-Pedro Mellado. Microhh 1.0: a computational fluid dynamics code for direct numerical simulation and large-eddy simulation of atmospheric boundary layer flows. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 10: 3145–3165, 2017. doi: 10.5194/gmd-10-3145-2017.

Ben van Werkhoven. Kernel Tuner: A search-optimizing GPU code auto-tuner. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 90:347–358, 2019.

Ben van Werkhoven, Willem Jan Palenstijn, and Alessio Sclocco. Lessons learned in a decade of research software engineering gpu applications. In *Computational Science – ICCS 2020*, pages 399–412, Cham, 2020. Springer International Publishing. ISBN 978-3-030-50436-6.

6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

Except the travel restrictions due to the pandemic, which imply remote collaboration with the granted project partners, no change was needed.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

European strategies for HPC in relation to the weather and climate community are in line with the macro-objectives of the ESiWACE2 project (see section 3). Indeed, the services provided have enabled European weather and climate models to take advantage of existing European pre-exascale and future exascale HPC systems, which include the capacity to scale and to use GPUs efficiently. Following this goal, we helped the community through three yearly open calls from 2020 to 2022 to profile, analyse, port on GPU and optimise their models. We strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem through these collaborations. For some of them (as FESOM2, OGSTM and RegCM) it is the impulsion toward a longer development effort and for others (as DALES, OBLIMAP2, AGRIF, EMAC, RTE+RRTMGP-CPP, BLOM and MicroHH) a booster to increase efficiency and to reinforce their leadership position in their particular domain. Last but not least, these service projects foster co-design between model developers, HPC experts from NLeSC and Atos, and also with HPC manufacturers and HPC centres because of the strong ties they maintain with them. Finally, this contributes to guiding the European weather and climate community on the road to a better exploitation of HPC resources in the service of science, decision-makers and all European citizens.

8 Sustainability

The work presented in this deliverable has been reported in multiple forms, including publications, presentations, posters, internal technical reports, and internal project deliverables.

All the code developments, code optimisations, etc. have been shared with the partners and on public repositories, most of the time in the main branch of the models. This ensures a long-lasting impact of this work, especially as it served as a first effort towards the use of technologies such as GPU accelerators.

Among the lessons learnt during these projects, the most important one is that close collaboration with the model developers leads to a more efficient service project and increases the impact on the code development and results. Also, the exchange of knowledge and experience between Atos and NLeSC has been instrumental

to achieve high-performance in several projects. Indeed, explanation, ideas and reciprocal knowledge exchanges demonstrate that it is key to create collaborations between HPC experts and scientific model developers to advance the state of weather and climate modeling. For some codes, including OGSTM, EMAC, FESOM2 and DALES, we have received repeated requests for 6-month service projects. In the case of FESOM2 and DALES, these extended projects have also been granted, which has enabled us to prolong the collaboration and have a larger impact on the model source code.

9 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

✓	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This deliverable will be publicly made available on the ESiWACE Zenodo repository. Results will be presented during community-based conferences.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

See Table 12, Table 13 and Table 14.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

See Table 15.

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

No intellectual property right resulted from this deliverable.

Table 12: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Participation to a conference	Erwan Raffin, Ben van Werkhoven, Florian Ziemer, "ESiWACE HPC services for Weather and Climate models toward production-ready simulation on European exascale systems", ISC Project Poster	22-25 June, 2020 (online)	Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3964547	4735
Exhibition	Teratec Forum Digital	2020 13-14 October (online)	Scientific Community, Industry, Civil Society, General Public, Policy makers, Medias, Investors, Customers		1200
Participation to a workshop	G. van den Oord, V. Azizi, A. Sclocco, G.E. Moulard, D. Guibert, J. Attema, E. Raffin, and B. van Werkhoven (presenter, panelist). ESiWACE2 Services: RSE collaborations in Weather and Climate. Research Software Engineers in HPC (RSE-HPC-2020) Workshop at Supercomputing (SC20) 2020.	12 November 2020 (online)	Scientific Community	recording not publicly available, https://us-rse.org/rse-hpc-2020/agenda/	103
Training	Ben van Werkhoven - Porting of Codes for Next Generation GPU Architectures	16 Dec 2020 (online)	Scientific Community	https://events.prace-ri.eu/event/1106/	20

Table 13: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable.

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Exhibition	Teratec Forum Digital	2021 22-24 June (online)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research), Industry, Civil Society, General Public, Policy makers, Medias, Investors, Customers		1200
Social media	Erwan Raffin, "Improving weather and climate forecasting – Why collaboration between domain scientists and High-Performance Computing experts is key", Atos online blog	28th June 2021 (online)	General Public	https://atos.net/en/blog/improving-weather-and-climate-forecasting-why-collaborate	N/A
Organisation of a workshop	Ben van Werkhoven, Alessio Sciocco, Floris-Jan Willemsen, Stijn Heldens - GPU Code Optimization and Auto-Tuning Made Easy with Kernel Tuner: A Hands-On, Bring Your Own Code Tutorial	14-19 November 2021 (St. Louis, MO, USA)	Scientific Community	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5798239	25
Participation to a conference	Erwan Raffin, Ben van Werkhoven, David Guibert, Julia Duras, "ESiWACE HPC Service for Weather and Climate Models Refactoring and Porting", ISC Project Poster	2022 31 May	Scientific Community		3007

Table 14: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable.

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Exhibition	Teratec Forum Digital	2022 14-15 June	Scientific Community (higher education, Research), Industry, Civil Society, General Public, Policy makers, Medias, Investors, Customers		1200
Participation to a conference	Gijs van den Oord, roundtable discussion participation on "Service complementarity of application needs throughout the HPC Pyramid", chaired by Edouard Audit	22-24 March 2022 (Paris, FR)	Scientific community, Industry	not available	30
Participation to a conference	Gijs van den Oord, 7th ENES HPC Workshop, Barcelona: Accelerating tracer transport in FE-SOM2 with GPU's	May 9th-11th 2022 (Barcelona, ES)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/record/6552990	80

Table 15: Publications related to this deliverable

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?
Published	The Landscape of Exascale Research: A Data-Driven Literature Analysis	S. Heldens, P. Hijma, B. van Werkhoven, J. Maassen, A.S.Z. Belloum, and R.V. van Nieuwpoort	ACM Computing Surveys	Open Access, https://doi.org/10.1145/3372390
Published	ESiWACE2 Services: RSE collaborations in Weather and Climate	G. van den Oord, V. Azizi, A. Sclocco, G.E. Moulard, D. Guibert, J. Attema, E. Raffin, and B. van Werkhoven	Research Software Engineers in HPC (RSE-HPC-2020) Workshop at Supercomputing (SC20)	Open Access, https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.14643
Published	Assessing uncertainties from physical parameters and modeling choices in an atmospheric LES model	F. Jansson, W. Edeling, J. Attema, D. Crommelin	Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A	Open Access, https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0073
Published	GPU Optimizations for Atmospheric Chemical Kinetics	T. Christoudias, T. Kirfel, A. Kerkweg, D. Taraborrelli, G.E. Moulard, E. Raffin, V. Azizi, G. van den Oord, B. van Werkhoven	HPC Asia 2021 Poster session	unknown
Published	OBLIMAP parallelization and optimization toward high resolution climate model - ice sheet model coupler	E. Raffin, D. Guibert, T. Reerink	EGU21	Open Access, https://doi.org/10.5194/2Fegusphere-egu21-9880
Published	Optimizations of multiscale simulation with AGRIF, towards exascale applications	G. Irrmann, S. Masson, L. Debreu, D. Guibert, and E. Raffin	EGU22	Open Access, https://doi.org/10.5194/2Fegusphere-egu22-12292
Published	GPU acceleration of the FESOM-2 ocean and sea-ice model	G. van den Oord, A. Sclocco, G.E. Moulard, D. Guibert, D. Sidorenko, N. Koldunov, B. van Werkhoven, E. Raffin, N. Rakowski	EGU21	Open Access, https://doi.org/10.5194/2Fegusphere-egu21-11551
Published	Optimization of RTE+RRTMGP-C++: a CUDA implementation of the radiation package RTE+RRTMGP for atmospheric science	G. van den Oord, A. Sclocco, B. van Stratum, M. Veerman, G.E. Moulard, D. Guibert, E. Raffin, B. van Werkhoven, C. van Heerwaarden	AGU21	unknown